

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This time you can see J.UCS in its new design, and we are still planning further improvements like e.g. making the annotation mechanism more visible. Also, a meeting with Springer is upcoming to decide on how to improve marketing for J.UCS.

Although this is a fairly slim volume, we still have a number of special issues planned for this year. Also, despite the approaching summer a number of new papers have been submitted.

Please enjoy reading this newest edition of the oldest and most successful digital journal in Computer Science (yes, this is our claim!) and help to keep it this way by staying in our fan club and also by submitting a good paper once in a while. Let me take this opportunity to thank our editors for their continuous help with reviewing and encouraging submissions!

Have a pleasant summer (if you are on the Northern hemisphere), and a bearable winter if you are living down-under!

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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